

FAILURE AND RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF IN-SERVICE REPAIRED COMPOSITES

Wei Feng¹, Fei Xu^{1*} and Jialei Yuan¹

¹ Institute for Computational Mechanics and Its Applications (NPUiCMA),
School of Aeronautics, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an, Shaanxi, China.

* Corresponding author (xufei@nwpu.edu.cn)

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ABSTRACT

Scarf-bonded technology has been widely used to joint or repair composite components in aircraft structures. Sometimes it is inevitable to perform repair directly on in-service components. In this paper, failure and reliability analysis of in-service repaired composites via scarf method were conducted. Tensile failure tests were carried out on scarf-repaired composites of three different laminate thicknesses to elucidate the repair efficiency and failure modes. The failure strengths of each group are relatively close and the typical failure modes are similar. In addition, a finite element model was established and it can predict the failure strength and damage mode well. Based on the validated model, the effects of adhesive shear strength and mode II fracture toughness were discussed. At last, Weibull function was used to analyze the scatter in the experimental results and safe failure strengths at different reliability and confidence levels were estimated using time to first failure concept.

1 INTRODUCTION

Considering the high cost of composite materials and its relatively inferior ability to bear impact load, composite structures face the repair problems. Bonded repair can be regarded as a versatile cost-effective method without compromising structural integrity. And scarf repair gets more uniform stress distribution and is often used for scenarios where smooth surface is needed to satisfy aerodynamic or stealth requirements [1-4].

In terms of in-service components, sometimes it is difficult to undertake repairing with an autoclave due to the structure configurations and repair conditions. Thus the repair process has to be undertaken in situ on an aircraft structures using vacuum bag cure. However, for autoclave cured composite materials, vacuum bagging is difficult to achieve low-void laminates of good quality, which harms the mechanical properties of composites [5]. For example, voids reduced values of the shear modulus and strength to 30% of their void free values at 5 % voids [6].

In addition, a characteristic feature of adhesive-bonded structures is that large variations in joint strength occur due to variations of the mechanical and geometrical properties of the joint constituents as well as due to variability of the manufacturing processes [7,8]. So reliability assessment is necessary to ensure the safety of repaired-composite structures. The establishment of a reliability based design methodology to predict the safe strength of scarf-repaired composite structures is of considerable importance in rational design.

In this work, in-service repair was undertaken by using an alternative material which shows better performance than the original material in vacuum bagging for the patch. Failure and reliability analysis of such scarf-repaired composites were investigated. Tensile failure tests were conducted on three groups of specimens with different laminate thicknesses to elucidate the repair efficiency and failure mode. In addition, a finite element model based on continuum damage model (CDM) and cohesive zone model (CZM) was established to predict the failure strength and damage mode. Based on the validated model, the influence of adhesive shear strength and mode II fracture toughness on the structure strength were analyzed. At last, reliability analysis was performed based on the time to first failure (TTF) concept [9]. The safe failure strength at different reliability and confidence levels were predicted.

2 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1 Specimen preparation

The configuration of scarf-repaired composite laminates specimens is shown in **Fig. 1**. Glass fiber end tabs of 2 mm thickness were bonded to the grip areas. 5228A/CCF300 epoxy/carbon unidirectional prepreg manufactured by Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials was used for the parent laminates. TC350-1/IM7-12K was selected for repair patch owing to its high permeability of resin. An overlap patch prepared by TC350-1/IM7-12K was added on the top of the patch to enhance the repair. Scarf repaired specimens of three different laminate thickness shown in **Table 1** were examined to elucidate the repair efficiency for composite subject to different load levels. All the specimens were cured at 180 °C and 0.1 MPa conditions for 2 hrs.

Fig. 1. The configuration of scarf repaired specimens

Table 1 Text matrix

Group	Substrates	Ply sequences	T(mm)	L(mm)
SCJ-A	Parent laminate	[45/0/-45/90/45/0 ₃ /-45/90/45/0 ₂ /-45]s	3.5	282
	Patch	[45/0/-45/90/45/0 ₃ /-45/90/45/0/-45]s		
SCJ-B	Parent laminate	[45/0/-45/90/45/0 ₃ /-45/90/45 ₂ /0 ₂ /-45/0 ₂ /-45]s	4.5	294
	Patch	[45/0/-45/90/45/0 ₃ /-45/90/45 ₂ /0 ₂ /-45/0/(0)]s		
SCJ-C	Parent laminate	[45/0/-45/90/45/0 ₃ /-45/90/45 ₂ /0 ₂ /-45/0 ₂ /-45 ₂ /0 ₃ /45 ₂ /0 ₂ /-45/90]s	7	324
	Patch	[45/0/-45/90/45/0 ₃ /-45/90/45 ₂ /0 ₂ /-45/0 ₂ /-45 ₂ /0 ₃ /45/0/-45/90]s		

2.2 Tensile test

Quasi-static tensile tests were carried out for all the specimens at room temperature (RT). The load was applied at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. The strength was taken as the maximum load recorded by the machine and computer. Five samples were tested for each test series.

2.3 Experimental results

The ultimate strength was obtained by dividing the maximum load by the cross-sectional area of parent laminates. The average strength and the coefficient of variation for each group are given in **Table 2**. The coefficient of variation of each group is relatively low. These low coefficients of variation demonstrate that the repair process is generally steady. The failure strengths of each group are relatively close, which indicates that the repair efficiency is steady for composite laminates of different thicknesses.

Table 2 Specimen number and tensile test results of scarf repaired laminates

Group	Thickness (mm)	Ultimate load (kN)	Strength (MPa)	CV (%)
SCJ-A	3.5	58.36	463.17	7.04
SCJ-B	4.5	68.61	423.52	5.65
SCJ-C	7	110.88	439.99	4.78

Fig. 2 shows the typical failure modes of the repaired specimens with various laminate thicknesses. Similar types of failure were found in all scarf joints irrespective of laminate thickness. Cohesive failure of adhesive, adhesive-composite interfacial debonding and intralaminar damage of composite

laminates along the bondline and fracture of the overlap patch were observed. Of the overall bonding areas of each group, the bulk of the adhesive remained on both of fracture scarf surfaces, which basically explained cohesive failure of adhesive was the dominated damage mode that caused the joint failure.

Fig. 2. Failure modes of specimens with different laminate thickness

3 NUMERICAL SIMULATION

3.1 Model description

A finite element model based on continuum damage model (CDM) and cohesive zone model (CZM) was established to predict the failure strength and damage mode. For composite laminate damage modelling, the strain based 3D Hashin criterion failure criteria were utilized with the distinct failure mode for tension and compression [10]. A user subroutine VUMAT in the ABAQUS finite element program was used to account for the onset of damage and stiffness degradation in the composite laminates. For adhesive damage modelling, the bilinear traction–separation law was adopted for damage initiation and damage evolution. The damage initiation was modelled as a quadratic stress interaction relationship. The damage evolution was based on power law fracture energy criterion. Fig. 3 shows a typical FE mesh for the SCJ with refinement around the bonding areas. According to the loading process during test, the model was fixed at one end and displacement load was applied at the other end. The detailed materials of composite laminates and adhesive can be seen in the work by the same authors [11].

Fig. 3. Boundary conditions and meshing of the scarf-repaired composites

3.2 Strength and damage prediction

A comparison of computational and experimental results is shown in Fig. 4. The predicted failure loads are in good agreement with experimental data (relative error below 10%). Good agreement was achieved between the predicted and experimental failure loads, which indicated that the finite element model is able to accurately predict the failure strength of scarf-repaired composites.

Fig. 4. Comparison between testing and FEM results

The final damage modes in **Fig. 5** agree well with the experimental results. Matrix crack of composite laminates, fracture of overlap patch and cohesive failure of adhesive are captured, which verifies the used model again.

Fig. 5. Comparison of final damage modes between test and FEM

3.3 Parameter study

Considering the adhesive layer of scarf-repaired composite is mainly subjected to shear stress, the influences of two parameters (shear strength and mode II fracture toughness) were investigated. From the numerical results shown in **Fig. 6**, it can be clearly seen that decrease of shear strength and mode II fracture toughness reduces the load capacity of the scarf-repaired composites. A linear relationship can be observed between the failure strength and the degradation of adhesive properties. Compared to mode II fracture toughness, the influence of adhesive shear strength on the failure strength of repaired composites is much obvious. When the mode II fracture toughness decreases 30%, the failure strength of repaired composites decreases only 2.3%. While, a decrease in failure strength of 25.9% is observed when shear strength decreases 30%.

Fig. 6. Influence of adhesive properties on the failure strength of scarf-repaired composites

4 RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

4.1 Scatter in the experimental results

Considering the variations of adhesive properties due to variability of the manufacturing process, it is necessary to evaluate the reliable strength for structural safety. So reliability assessment is necessary to ensure the safety of repaired-composite structures. The establishment of a reliability based design methodology to predict the safe strength. The two-parameter Weibull distribution function was used to investigate the statistical and reliability analyses of the experimental results of scarf-repaired composites with different laminate thicknesses. The probability density function (PDF) and cumulative distribution function (CDF) of Weibull distribution are shown as

$$f(x)|_{Weibull} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta} \left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^{\alpha-1} \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right] \quad x \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

$$F(x)|_{Weibull} = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right] \quad (2)$$

x is a random variable, α and β are the shape and scale parameters of Weibull function, respectively. **Eq.(2)** can be rewritten as **Eq.(3)** by taking the logarithm of both sides.

$$\ln\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-F(x)}\right) = -\alpha\ln\beta + \alpha\ln x \quad (3)$$

By setting $X=\ln x$, $Y=\ln\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-F(x)}\right)$, $A=-\alpha\ln\beta$, $B=\alpha$, the standard linear regression equation can be obtained as **Eq. (4)**

$$Y=A+BX \quad (4)$$

The empirical frequency function is defined as follow:

$$F(x_i) = \frac{i}{n+1} \quad (5)$$

n is the sample number and i is the serials number of the fatigue life data in ascending order at the same given stress level.

The two-parameter Weibull distribution for ultimate strength (σ_u) were plotted in **Fig. 7**. The abscissa is $\ln(\sigma_u)$ and the ordinate is $\ln\ln[1/(1-F(\sigma_u))]$. It has a linear relationship in accordance with Eq. (4). The values of α and β were calculated by the least squares curve fitting from figure 7. Therefore, the slopes (α) of the lines in Fig.7 can effectively represent the scatter in the failure strength data of the scarf-repaired composites. The lower the slope, the larger the scatter.

Fig.7. Weibull ultimate strength distribution. Fig.8. Weibull normalized ultimate strength distribution

4.2 Safe fatigue life based on time to first failure (TTFF) concept

Safe design failure strength ($\sigma_{R\gamma}$) based on TTFF concept was estimated as follow:

$$\sigma_{R\gamma} = \frac{\hat{\beta}}{S_M \cdot S_N \cdot S_R} \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{\beta} = \left(\frac{\sum_{m=1}^i x_i^{\alpha_n}}{m} \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha_n}} \quad (7)$$

$\hat{\beta}$ is characteristic bearing strength. α_n is the normalized shape parameter, which is estimated by plotting the normalized failure strength values (x_i/β) in Weibull probability paper with abscissa equal to $\ln(x_i/\beta)$ and the ordinate equal to $\ln\ln[1/(1-F(x_i/\beta))]$, as shown in **Fig.8**. m is the finite sample size. In this study, $m=2$ (the first two lowest failure strengths).

S_M , S_N , and S_R are the sample size factor, fleet size factor, and reliability factor, respectively [12,13]. The values of S_M , S_N , and S_R can be calculated by:

$$S_M = \left(\frac{1}{2m} X_\gamma^2(2m) \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha_n}} \quad (8)$$

$$S_N = \left(\frac{1}{n} \right)^{\frac{-1}{\alpha_n}} \quad (9)$$

$$S_R = \left(\ln \left(\frac{1}{R} \right) \right)^{\frac{-1}{\alpha_n}} \quad (10)$$

where $X_\gamma^2(2m)$ is the chi-square distribution of $2m$ degree of freedom, its value will vary at different confidence levels. n is the number of tests for each condition, and R is reliability.

Based on time to first failure (TTFF) concept, the safe failure strength of scarf-repaired composite laminates at various reliability and confidence levels were calculated and shown in **Fig. 9** and **Fig. 10**, respectively. And based on the distribution of each group in **Fig.7**, the safe failure strength can also directly predicted and plotted in dash line in **Fig. 9**, too. The results shows that at the same reliability

and confidence level ($R=0.99, \gamma=0.99$), TTFF concept can get more conservative strength.

Fig. 9. Safe strength at various reliability ($\gamma=0.99$) Fig.10. Safe strength at various confidence levels($R=0.99$)

In addition, it can be seen from **Fig.9** and **Fig.10** that the safe failure strength decreases with the increasing of reliability or confidence level. In addition, the safe failure strength will decrease more when reliability increases to the same degree than the confidence level, comparing with a baseline. For example, the safe strength decreases about 20% from $R=0.5$ to $R=0.99$ ($\gamma=0.99$), while when the confidence level increase from 0.5 to 0.99 ($R=0.99$), the safe strength only decreases about 7%.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The present work deals with the failure and reliability analysis of in-service repaired composites via scarf method. The major results and conclusions are summarized as follows.

The experimental results show that average tensile strengths of the scarf repaired composite laminates are 463.17 MPa, 423.52 MPa, and 439.99 MPa for 3.5 mm, 4.5 mm, and 7 mm thick specimens, respectively. This indicates that the repair efficiency is steady for composite laminates with different thicknesses. Failure modes of different groups are similar. The dominated failure mode is cohesive failure of adhesive.

The numerical model based on CDM and CZM can predict the strength and failure modes accurately. Numerical analysis shows that there is a linear relationship between the failure strength of scarf-repaired composites and the adhesive shear strength or mode II fracture toughness. Compared to mode II fracture toughness, the influence of adhesive shear strength on the failure strength of repaired composites is much obvious.

Time to first failure (TTFF) concept was used to predict the safe failure strengths at different reliability and confidence levels. The results show that the safe failure strength decreases with confidence level or reliability increasing. However, safe failure strength reduce more heavily when reliability increasing to the same degree than confidence level.

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